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THE FLORA AND VEGETATION OF EASTERN GEORGIA IN THE SARMATIAN

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Abstract

The full sections of Sarmatian deposits of Eastern Georgia were studied by palynological method. The landscape-phytocenological analysis of material reflects the changes of ecological-systematical composition of flora and allows to follow the evolution of vegetation in Kartli and Kakheti depending on climatic fluctuations.

Key words: Eastern Georgia, Sarmatian, palynology.

Introduction

Sarmatian deposits are widely distributed on the territory of Eastern Georgia and are divided into three substages: Volhinian (Lower), Bessarabian (Middle) and Khersonian (Upper). The Lower and Middle Sarmatian are built by marine deposits. The thick series of continental deposits of Natskhorian suit, which has a wide distribution and is the part of most syncline and anticline folds, belongs to the Upper Sarmatian in Kartli.

The Upper Sarmatian on the territory of Kakheti is different. In the North-Western part of region it is represented by continental deposits of Eldarian suit, with tests of freshwater and terrestrial gastropoda. Towards the south-east the clays of lower part of Eldarian suit are replaced by marine sediments with fauna of Mactra [Buleishvili, 1960; Koiava, 2006]. The presence of “marine suit” is confirmed also by micropaleontological investigations of core material from boreholes [Maissuradze et al., 2006].

Materials and Methods

Until recently the most of our knowledge on the Sarmatian flora of Eastern Georgia was based on macrobotanical data [Uznadze, 1965; Chelidze, 1987]. Whole material is connected with deposits of the Lower and Middle Sarmatian. By palynological method only some core samples from Central part of the Kartli depression were studied [Mchedlishvili, Mchedlishvili, 1953]. In spite of poorness of fossil material (28 forms), the palynological assemblages, typical for three substages of the Sarmatian were distinguished.

Now the rich body of palynological material was collected from full sections of Sarmatian deposits on the territory of Kartli (sections Nadarbazevi, Aragvi) and Kakheti (sections Davit

Gareji, Gombori). The palynological assemblages were interpreted by landscape-phytocenological method [Borzenkova, 1992], The whole composition of palynoflora was divided into some ecological groups of plants: the conifers of temperate climate (*Abies*, *Picea*, *Tsuga*); subtropical and warm-temperate conifers (*Podocarpus*, *Dacrydium*, *Cathaya*, *Keteleeria*, *Cedrus*); warm-temperate leaf-bearing plants (*Carya*, *Juglans*, *Fagus*, *Quercus*, *Carpinus*, *Zelkova* and others); subtropical leaf-bearing plants (the representatives of families *Myricaceae*, *Fagaceae*, *Lauraceae*, *Hamamelidaceae*, *Araliaceae*, *Icacinaceae*, *Alangiaceae*, *Arecaceae*); subtropical ferns (*Anemia*, *Lygodium*, *Mohria*, *Cyathea*, *Dicksonia*, *Cleichenia*, *Pteris*, *Polypodium*); xerophyllous plants of woodless areas (the representatives of families *Chenopodiaceae*, *Asteraceae*, *Poaceae* and others). Two palynological diagrams were built. One for Kartli on the basis of material from Nadarbazevi section (Fig. 1) and second - for Kakheti based on the palynological material from Gombori section (Fig.2). The curves of these diagrams reflect the changes in composition in mentioned above groups during the Lower, Middle and Upper Sarmatian. The curve of pine, as an intrazonal plant and index of humidity, is given separately.

As a whole based on palynological data in the composition of Sarmatian flora of Eastern Georgia nearly 200 elements belonging to 137 genera and 93 families, were determined: *Sphagnum* sp., *Lycopodium serratum* Thumb., *Lycopodium* sp., *Selaginella* sp., *Selaginella fusca* N. Mchedl., *Botrychium* sp., *Ophioglossum* sp., *Osmunda cinnamomea* L., *Osmunda* sp., *Schizaea* sp., *Schizaeaceae* gen.indet., *Anemia* sp., *Mohria* sp., *Lygodium digitatum* Presl., *Lygodium japonicum* Sw., *Lygodium* aff. *multivallatum* (W.Kr.) Ram., *Lygodium* sp., *gramma* sp., *Pteridacidites longifoliiformis* Sh. et St., *Pteridacidites venustaeformis* Sh. et St., *Pteridacidites* aff. *verus* (N. Mchedl.) Sh. et St., *Pteridacidites* aff. *vittatoides* Shat. Stuch., *P. guriensis* Sh. et St., *P. grandifoliiformis* St. et Sh., *P. boerzoenyensis* St. et Sh. (Nagy), *P. dentatiformis* Sh. et St., *Pteridacidites* sp., *Pteris* sp., *Marsilea* sp., *Anogramma* sp., *Onychium* sp., *Pityrogramma* sp., *Clavifera* aff. *tuberosa* Bolch., *Clavifera* sp., *Gleichenia* sp., *Gleicheniaceae* gen. indet., *Polypodium aureum* L., *Polypodium verrucatum* Ram., *Polypodium* sp., *Polypodium plicenicum* Ram., *Verrucatosporites histiopteroides* W. Kr., *Pyrrosia* sp., *Polypodiaceae* gen.indet., *Hymenophyllum* sp., *Cibotium* sp., *Dicksonia spanditocincta* Pure., *Dicksonia unitotuberosa* Pure., *Dicksonia* sp., *Dicksonia reticulata* Pure., *Alsophylla* sp., *Cyathea* sp., *Hemitelia* sp., *Asplenium* sp., *Cystopteris* sp., *Dryopteris* sp., *Microlepia* sp., *Thelypteris* sp., *Woodsia* sp., *Polystichum* sp., *Ginkgo* sp., *Dacrydium* sp., *Podocarpus* sp., *Phyllocladus* sp., *Araucaria* sp., *Abies alba* Mill., *Abies ciliicaeformis* N. Mchedl., *Abies nordmanniana* (Stev.) Spach., *Abies* sp., *Cathaya* sp., *Cedrus deodara* Loud., *Cedrus saueriae* N. Mchedl., *Cedrus* sp., *Keteleeria caucasica* Ram., *Picea complanataeformis* N. Mchedl., *Picea minor* N. Mchedl., *Picea* sp., *Pinus rjabini* Palib., *Pinus* sp., *Pseudolarix* sp., *Pseudotsuga* sp., *Tsuga* aff. *diversifolia* (Maxim.) Mast., *Tsuga* aff. *canadensis* (L.) Carr., *Tsuga* aff. *pattoniana* Engelm., *Tsuga* sp., *Pinaceae* gen.indet., *Sciadopitys* sp., *Cryptomeria* sp., *Cunninghamia* sp., *Sequoia* sp., *Metasequoia* sp., *Sequoiadendron* sp., *Taxodium* sp., *Taxodiaceae* gen. indet., *Juniperus* sp., *Libocedrus* sp., *Juniperus* sp., *Cupressaceae* gen. indet., *Ephedra* sp., *Comptonia* sp., *Myrica* sp., *Myrica* aff. *notabilis* Gladk., *Myricaceae* gen. indet., *Carya aquatica* (Michx.) Nutt., *Carya cordiformis* (Wangh.) C. Koch, *Carya* sp., *Carya ovata* Mill., *Carya* aff. *glabra* (Mill.) Sweet, *Engelhardia* sp., *Juglans cinerea* L., *Juglans regia* L., *Juglans* sp., *Platycarya* sp., *Pterocarya pterocarpa* (Michx.) Kunth., *Pterocarya* aff. *stenoptera* DC, *Pterocarya* sp., *Juglandaceae* gen.indet., *Salix* sp., *Alnus* sp., *Betula* sp., *Carpinus betulus* L., *Carpinus caucasica* Grossh., *Carpinus orientalis* Mill., *Carpinus* sp., *Corylus* sp., *Castanea* sp., *Castanopsis* sp., *Lithocarpus* sp., *Fagus* sp., *Quercus* sp., *Celtis* sp., *Ulmus foliacea* Gilib., *Ulmus* sp., *Zelkova carpiniifolia* (Pall.) Dipp., *Zelkova serrata* (Thinb.) Makino, *Zelkova* sp., *Ulmaceae* gen.indet., *Eucommia ulmoides* Oliv., *Ficus* sp., *Moraceae* gen.indet, *Polygonaceae* gen. indet., *Caryophyllaceae* gen.indet., *Chenopodiaceae* gen. indet., *Liriodendron* sp., *Magnolia megafigurata* (Krutsch) comb, nov Ram., *Magnolia grandiflora* L., *Magnolia* sp., *Annona* sp.,

Cinnamomum sp., *Laurus* sp., *Lauraceae* gen. indet., *Ranunculus* sp., *Berberidaceae* gen. indet., *Menispermum* sp., *Nuphar* sp., *Nymphaea* sp., *Nymphaeaceae* gen. indet., *Brassicaceae* gen. indet., *Aristolochia* sp., *Papaver* sp., *Platanus* sp., *Corylopsis* sp., *Disanthus* aff. *cercidifolia* Maxim., *Disanthus* sp., *Fothergilla* sp., *Hamamelis* sp., *Parrotia* sp., *Sycopsis* sp., *Sycopsis colchica* Ram., *Liquidambar* sp., *Liquidambar styraciflua* L., *Hamamelidaceae* gen.indet, *Cercidiphyllum* sp., *Pyrus theobroma* Ung., *Sorbus* sp., *Rosaceae* gen.indet., *Acacia* sp., *Fabaceae* gen.indet., *Geranium* sp., *Rhus* sp., *Acer* sp., *Aesculus* sp., *Ilex* sp., *Icacinaceae* gen.indet., *Euonymus* sp., *Staphylea* sp., *Buxus* sp., *Parthenocissus* sp., *Vitis* sp., *Tilia caucasica* Rupr., *Tilia* aff. *cordata* Mill., *Tilia* aff. *platyphyllos* Scop., *Tilia* sp., *Sterculia* sp., *Elaeagnus* sp., *Viola* sp., *Myrtaceae* gen.indet., *Onagraceae* gen.indet., *Alangium* sp., *Nyssa* sp., *Cornaceae* gen.indet., *Acanthopanax* sp., *Aralia* sp., *Brassaiopsis* sp., *Dendropanax* sp., *Fatsia* sp., *Araliaceoipollenites edmundi* (Pot.) Pot., *Araliaceae* gen.indet., *Apiaceae* gen.indet., *Arbutus guriensis* Uzn., *Rhododendron* sp., *Ericaceae* gen.indet., *Sapotaceae* gen.indet., *Symplocos* sp., *Apocynaceae* gen.indet., *Convolvulus* sp., *Fraxinus* sp., *Oleaceae* gen.indet., *Lonicera* sp., *Viburnum* sp., *Lamiaceae* gen.indet., *Plantago* sp., *Valeriana* sp., *Knautia* sp., *Scabiosa* sp., *Dipsacaceae* gen.indet., *Achillea* sp., *Artemisia* sp., *Cichorium* sp., *Asteraceae* gen.indet., *Liliaceae* gen.indet., *Poaceae* gen. indet., *Nipa* sp., *Arecaceae* gen.indet., *Pandanus* sp., *Sparganium* sp., *Typha latissima* A.Br., *Typha* sp., *Fupingopollenites wackersdorfensis* (Thiele-Pfeiffer) Liu Geng-wu., *Fupingopollenites minutus* Liu Geng-wu.

Fig.1. Fluctuations in pollen percentages indicating changes in composition of separate ecological groups of plants in the Sarmatian of Kartli (section Nadarbasevi)

Fig.2. Fluctuations in pollen percentages indicating changes in composition of separate ecological groups of plants in the Sarmatian of Kakheti (section Gombori)

Results and Discussion

Judging from the palynological assemblages and macroremains of plants the main formation on the territory of Eastern Georgia during the Early and Middle Sarmatian was the polydominant forest.

The more termophilous and hygrophylous plants inhabited in the littoral zone and in lower mountain belt. The components of forest were representatives of families Lauraceae, Araliaceae, Sapotaceae, Icacinaceae, Areaceae. The lower layer of forest formed the arborescent and grassy ferns: *Dicksonia*, *Cyathea*, *Lygodium*, *Anemia*, *Pteris*, *Polypodium*. Among these forms the last genera predominated. The components of riparian forest were *Liquidambar*, *Nyssa*, *Pterocarya*, *Ulmus*, *Carya* and some *Hamamelidaceae*.

On the territories situated far from the accumulation basin dominated the deciduous forest. In its composition were: *Quercus*, *Castanea*, *Fagus*, *Juglans*, *Carpinus*, *Zelkova*, *Platanus*, *Tilia*. The leaf-bearing plants were mixed with gymnosperms: *Ginkgo*, *Dacrydium*, *Podocarpus*, *Cathaya*, *Keteleeria*, *Cedrus*.

The upper levels of relief were occupied by *Abies*, *Picea* *Tsuga*. The area of dark conifer forest was small in comparison with polydominant formation. The pine was the component of different cenosis and occupied the big territories.

The palynological assemblages of the Lower and Middle Sarmatian deposits of Kartli reflect the vegetation, which developed in conditions of subtropical climate with low humidity. Somewhat other situation was on territory of Kakheti. Here the role of pine was smaller and the part of thermophilous and hygrophilous elements of flora in composition of polydominant forest was much greater. Among ferns such forms as Mohria, Anemia, Lygodium, Gleichenia, dominated.

The boundary between the Middle and Upper Sarmatian in Kartli is led by appearance of conglomerate layer, indicating the changes in process of sedimentation [Koiava. 2006]. In all sections studied by palynological method the deposits of Khersonian substage distinguished by composition of pollen assemblages, which reflect the changes in vegetation. In the Late Sarmatian the area of forest formation reduced and the territory of woodless significantly increased. All these phenomena more distinctly were manifested in Kartli and in smaller degree in Kakheti, on the plot near Gombori, which distinguished by local microclimate conditions. Nevertheless even the part of xerophilous plant in composition of vegetational cover was increased here.

Conclusion

The characteristic sign of Sarmatian vegetation of Eastern Georgia was the predominance of subtropical and warm-temperate plants. In composition of cenosis the hard-leaved and moist-subtropical components were represented. Already in the Sarmatian the differences between vegetation of Kartli and Kakheti are observed. In Kartli the development of vegetation in the Early and Middle Sarmatian was gone in conditions of low humidity, that in the Late Sarmatian and in the following stretches of Neogene led to full succession of forest formations by woodless areas [Mchedlishvili, Mchedlishvili, 1953; Meladze, 1967]. In Kakheti the changes in character of vegetation on the boundary of the Middle and Upper Sarmatian was not so sharp, especially in the northern part of the region.

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მცენარეულობა

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